

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF HUMAN CAPITAL AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article examines the theory of increasing the quality of human capital and its significant impact on sustainable development. Uzbekistan attaches great importance to ensuring sustainable development. To achieve this, the role of human capital in the current environment, as well as the implementation of necessary measures to increase quality indicators reflecting the level of human capital development, social infrastructure, education and health care systems, is one of the main tasks.

Key words: human capital, sustainable development, investment, sustainable economic growth, performance indicators, social infrastructure, — innovative economy, knowledge, experience, ability.

Introduction: Human capital, without a doubt, appears as a priority direction of social economic policy in Uzbekistan today, where a person and his abilities, knowledge, and skills have become the main factor for the well-being of any society and the economic development of the state. Because the development of human capital is considered a necessary condition for the development of innovative economy, knowledge economy, investments, global information systems, the latest technologies and new forms of business. Human capital is a collection of knowledge and skills used to meet various needs of a person and society as a whole. Among the various characteristics that make up human potential, human capital represents the characteristics that affect the change of income, in this respect, human capital includes the knowledge, practical

application and skills of the worker accumulated on the basis of special education, vocational training and production experience.

The main part: World experience and practice show that the countries that have chosen investment in human capital as a priority achieve high development. In recent years, investment in human capital has been considered as a factor of long-term stable economic growth. In the last two or three years, attention has been paid to the development of human capital, which is considered an integral part of national wealth. These include social protection, human health, improvement of family relations, improvement of activities of neighborhood institutions, and fundamental changes in the education system. Economic development caused the formation of the concept of human capital and made it an integral part of world civilization. Gerry Becker (1930) was the author of the work "Human capital" (1964), in his opinion, human capital has a higher return on capital than technical technologies, and for its development, it is necessary to invest in training future specialists and improving the skills of those who work.

Economists divide human capital into two aspects according to their results:

1. Human capital as a reserve.

Human capital is a person's reserve health, knowledge, experience, ability, increasing work efficiency through motivations and, as a result, income leads to an increase. It usually includes the following:

- Congenital ability;
- Spirituality;
- General and special knowledge;
- Being able to use knowledge in the right place at the right time.

2. Human capital as a revenue stream

Investing capital in human capital as a key asset throughout its life becomes a source of income. The emergence of the theory of human capital is intangible in recent years capital accumulation led to human development. Human capital means people all performance indicators are understood, i.e. knowledge acquisition, competence increase, and motivation and energy to increase economic efficiency is

used. Investments in human capital usually mean education, education, health care, and human retraining and improvement of skills expenses incurred for , In general, human capital is labor productivity as mentioned above or increase in skills only through investment in them can be increased. This process is called education (knowledge).

As we mentioned, this process can be taken continuously from work. We can reject the law of diminishing returns, if we are one if we invest in human capital and physical capital at the same time. This because the model assumes constant efficiency (physical and human permanent income from the sum of their capitals), then if physical and human If we double our capital, then we have double the profit will have opportunities.

Conclusion: Continuity is the main factor in improving human capital or skills

is an educational system conducted People school and other we consider them to be those who have given up their wages after studying in educational institutions.

Because if instead of getting an education, they work in some enterprise they would have received a certain salary. Economists of such a process are human In general, which alternative path should we choose for economic growth and sustainable development?

We called the first option elitism: a certain group of people are good they get information, because the economic development depends on their state depends on management. According to this theory, if the leaders are well informed if they have, then the country is said to develop stably. We called the second option universalism: every person has minimum knowledge should get The essence of this option is that it is economical from each worker growth is that new technologies must be introduced quickly. Last 30 The economic growth in East Asia during the years was first in sewing, then in watches and began with the production of radio products. The level of quality in these countries is slowly increased, and then these countries to other countries began to provide financial support. In such an

economic system, each worker must occupy various professions. Therefore, in such conditions, it is necessary to create such an educational system, which should help workers to acquire various professions.

In the last 30 years, the model of human capital accumulation is based on universalism is preferable to the model based on elitism

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